

β -Triazolinonylpropionamidoximes and their Derivatives

S. SOMASEKHARA & N. V. UPADHYAYA

Sarabhai Research Centre, Baroda

Received 15 March 1971

Amidoximes and amidines having heterocyclic substituents in the terminal position of an alkyl chain have been reported¹⁻³ to possess antihypertensive properties. So, the present study of β -(1,2,4-triazolin-5-on-1-yl)-propionamidoximes and their carbamyl derivatives was undertaken.

The 1-cyanoethyl-1,2,4-triazolin-5-ones required for this study were prepared by methods reported⁴ earlier by us. The cyanoethyltriazolinones were reacted with hydroxylamine in aqueous ethanol to obtain the corresponding amidoximes in 40-60% yields. The amidoximes were converted to their *o*-carbamyl derivatives by reaction with potassium cyanate in 80-90% yields, following the procedure of Buyle, Lenaers and Eloy⁵.

The triazolinonylpropionamidoximes and their carbamyl derivatives (Table 1) were screened for their analgesic and anti-inflammatory properties by reported methods,^{6,7} using aspirin and butazolidine respectively as standards. Only one of them (No. 5) showed analgesic properties equal to those of aspirin.

EXPERIMENTAL

β -(4-Phenyl-1,2,4-triazolin-5-on-1-yl)-propionamidoxime : β -(4-Phenyl-1,2,4-triazolin-5-on-1-yl)-propionitrile (4.28 g; 0.02 mole), hydroxylamine hydrochloride (1.53 g; 0.022 mole) and potassium carbonate (1.52; 0.011 mole) were taken in 80% ethanol (200 ml.). The reaction mixture was stirred and heated at 60-70° for 8 hrs. The solvents were distilled off *in vacuo*. The residue was washed with water (20 ml.) and then with benzene (20 ml.). The insoluble solids were crystallised from aqueous ethanol to obtain the title product; m.p. 169-70°; 2.2 g.

The rest of the propionamidoxime derivatives were similarly prepared. As compound 3 was water-soluble, it was purified by repeated crystallisations from alcohol-benzene.

o-Carbamyl- β -(4-Phenyl-1,2,4-triazolin-5-on-1-yl)-propionamidoxime : β -(4-Phenyl-1,2,4-triazolin-5-on-1-yl)-propionamidoxime (2.47 g; 0.01 mole) was dissolved in ice-cold 1*N* hydrochloric acid (12 ml) and treated with a solution of potassium cyanate (1 g.). After 1 hr at 10°, the reaction mixture was rendered alkaline with a drop of ammonia when the crude title product separated out. It was crystallised from ethanol; m.p. 142-43°; 2.4 g.

The rest of *o*-carbamyl derivatives reported were similarly prepared.

TABLE I

Analytical data of 1,2,4-triazolin-5-on-1-yl derivatives

No.	R ₁	R ₂	R ₃	m.p. °C	Nitrogen %	
					Found	Required
1	H	H	Phenyl	169-70	28.13	28.34
2	CONH ₂	H	Phenyl	142-43	29.11	28.97
3	H	CH ₃	Phenyl	170-71	26.96	26.82
4	CONH ₂	CH ₃	Phenyl	182-83	27.24	27.36
5	H	H	<i>o</i> -Tolyl	136-37	26.93	26.82
6	CONH ₂	H	<i>o</i> -Tolyl	184-86	27.48	27.36
7	H	CH ₃	<i>o</i> -Tolyl	119-20	25.57	25.46
8	CONH ₂	CH ₃	<i>o</i> -Tolyl	199-200	26.71	26.45
9	H	H	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	182-83	26.91	26.82
10	CONH ₂	H	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	191-92	27.29	27.36
11	H	CH ₃	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	171-73	25.64	25.46
12	CONH ₂	CH ₃	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	186-87	26.69	26.45
13	H	H	<i>p</i> -Anisyl	156-57	25.45	25.27
14	CONH ₂	H	<i>p</i> -Anisyl	150-51	26.17	26.25
15	H	CH ₃	<i>p</i> -Anisyl	195-96	23.91	24.05
16	CONH ₂	CH ₃	<i>p</i> -Anisyl	188-89	25.13	25.16
17	H	H	<i>o</i> -Chlorophenyl	173-75	24.62	24.86
18	CONH ₂	H	<i>o</i> -Chlorophenyl	189-91	25.93	25.89
19	H	CH ₃	<i>o</i> -Chlorophenyl	139-40	23.85	23.69
20	CONH ₂	CH ₃	<i>o</i> -Chlorophenyl	202-03	24.68	24.82

All melting-points are uncorrected.

REFERENCES

1. R. P. Mull, P. Schmidt, M. R. Dapero, J. Higgins and M. J. Weisbach, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, **80**, 3769.
2. R. P. Mull, M. E. Egbert and M. R. Dapero, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1960, **25**, 1953.
3. R. P. Mull, R. H. Mizzomi, M. R. Dapero and M. E. Egbert, *J. Med. Pharm. Chem.*, 1962, **5**, 651.
4. S. Somasekhara, N. V. Upadhyaya and S. L. Mukherjee, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, (in press).
5. R. Buyle, R. Lenaers and F. Eloy, *Helv. Chim. Acta.*, 1964, **47**, 790.
6. L. B. Witkin, C. F. Huebner, F. Galdi, E. O. Keefe, P. Spitaletta and A. J. Plummer, *J. Pharmacol. Exptl. Therap.*, 1961, **133**, 400.
7. C. A. Winter, E. A. Risley and G. W. Nuss, *J. Pharmacol. Exptl. Therap.*, 1963, **141**, 369.